

PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATION AND MULTILINGUALISM IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION

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Abstract

Early childhood education in Romania has undergone dynamic development over the past two decades, supported by legislative reforms that have regulated the functioning of institutions providing early childhood education. In this context, the present paper aims to examine several innovative approaches in early educational practices.

One such approach is the integrated content model, framed as a curricular necessity arising from the child's natural need to explore, understand, and master

the surrounding physical and social environment. This approach focuses on bringing together diverse knowledge, skills, and abilities around themes that spark children's interest in learning or that emerge from everyday life.

Another innovative approach is CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), which can be applied in both preschool and primary education to support the integrated acquisition of a foreign language alongside educational content. The document highlights the importance of early introduction of foreign languages, emphasizing the cognitive, linguistic, and socio-emotional benefits of this approach for young learners. It also underscores the teacher's role as a facilitator of active and communicative learning, capable of creating natural contexts for foreign language use through play, exploration, and interdisciplinary activities adapted to the preschool developmental stage.

Keywords: early education, content-integrated approach, CLIL approach

1. Introduction

The need for a systemic approach within early childhood education has underpinned the implementation of numerous educational policies in this field, centred on strategic objectives aimed at achieving inclusive education by ensuring access for all children, promoting equal opportunities, and strengthening the competencies of early childhood education professionals.

European and national strategies, alongside early childhood education projects, have created a complementary framework for regulating and improving early childhood education.

The *National Strategy for the Sustainable Development of Romania 2030*, adopted in 2018, provides for ensuring access to education for all children and guaranteeing equal opportunities in order to support lifelong learning through educational programmes and broadly defined curricular models, ranging from care and early education to formal programmes. *The National Strategy for the*

Protection and Promotion of Children’s Rights “Protected Children, Safe Romania” 2023–2027, adopted in 2023, sets out objectives for the effective implementation of children’s rights in all areas of life by ensuring access to quality public services. It highlights four essential services that must be guaranteed for young children: early education and care, health, nutrition, and housing.

In conjunction with other national strategies, the *National Strategy for Supporting Parents 2024–2030*, adopted in 2024, develops a unified framework for parental interventions, reinforcing the role of parents in supporting early childhood development. This aligns with the Ministry of Education’s priority objectives: ensuring equal educational opportunities for all children and promoting equity; fostering each child’s developmental potential; centring the educational system on the child; ensuring inclusion and enhancing educational quality; raising functional literacy levels; providing high-quality teacher training; and reducing early school leaving, among others.

These strategies are supported by European-level frameworks. The OECD (2020) identifies four actions that policymakers can implement to enhance early equity: ensuring access to early education and care for all disadvantaged children; providing education that responds to the needs of children and their families; strengthening partnerships between early childhood education centres and parents; and improving the quality of children’s home learning environments.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. Early Childhood Education – Directions for Action in Public Policy

Theoretical perspectives on early childhood education are in constant evolution, offering a comprehensive view of conceptual delineations, action orientations, and good practices implemented within educational institutions, as

well as extensive statistical data on the numerical trends of children enrolled in such settings.

Since the mid-nineteenth century, the “tradition” of early childhood has shaped a model centred on shifting societal perceptions regarding children’s need for free play, education, and care, and on understanding childhood as a distinct stage of human development (Wood, 2023). Early childhood education and care represent a fundamental right for all children and a foundation for lifelong learning (European Commission, 2025).

Early childhood education is also a form of family-support policy that many countries implement as a measure of social and economic well-being (Tolani & Brooks-Gunn, 2008). Measures in this regard are reflected in institutional development programmes designed to uphold children’s rights to assistance— including adequate care and nutrition—and to guarantee special protection from all forms of neglect, abuse, exploitation, and other conditions detrimental to their development (Valanzuela, 2010).

Early childhood education and care constitute a systematic intervention aimed at supporting the development of young children from birth to the age of six, a period that marks the onset of formal schooling in most countries (Correia, Camilo, Aguiar, & Amaro, 2019). It is a systemic approach through which children are guided to adapt to external demands, benefiting from the support and guidance of professionals (educators, parents) (Clipa, 2023). Considered a priority domain for research, early childhood education provides fertile ground for the development of interdisciplinary approaches and the emergence of new professional concerns and directions (Junier, 2023).

Within early childhood education institutions, complex integrated services are developed to ensure an optimal environment for children’s growth, turning these institutions into educational and therapeutic hubs in which

educational, medical, psychological, and counselling services converge (Costin, A., in Roman, Balaş et al., 2025). The early childhood education institution becomes the setting in which multidisciplinary teams—early childhood teachers, school counsellors, psychologists, medical professionals, among others—collaboratively assume shared responsibilities for children’s cultural and social development by engaging in joint decision-making and fulfilling differentiated roles within the educational environment.

2.2. Innovative Directions in the Content-Integrated Approach in Early Childhood Education

In an educational context, the development of children’s behaviours is a central objective of pedagogical practice. Educational interventions carried out by teachers facilitate communication among children and between children and adults, enabling them to support one another, to learn about the world, and to exercise their imagination and creative capacities (Pramling et al., 2019). Thus, communication and language behaviours, as well as cognitive, socio-emotional, and creative behaviours, become the focus of professional intervention.

Advancing the idea that the most effective way to learn science is by engaging in scientific activity (Brenneman & Stevenson-Boyd, 2009) and building on children’s intrinsic need to explore and understand, early childhood education provides valuable resources for the development of STEM practices as a transdisciplinary approach to the sciences (Wang & Mihai, 2025). With the expansion of STEM through the inclusion of the arts, the STEAM approach emerges as an integrative, transdisciplinary initiative emphasising creativity, design, and visual thinking. The benefits of these approaches are reflected in children’s formative achievements, particularly in their ability to apply knowledge practically within real-life projects. STEM and STEAM challenge

children within learning situations, fostering critical thinking, problem solving, creativity, innovation, exploration, collaboration, and adaptability.

The educator designs educational actions that facilitate the child's direct contact with nature, understood as a real environment for exploration and development, thereby opening educational alternatives through PROJECT-BASED learning and OUTDOOR education. Grounded in the principles of experiential learning, these approaches support authentic learning in real contexts, promote each child's personal engagement in tasks, and encourage involvement in real community issues. They enable the educator to create interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary learning activities anchored in the practical challenges of everyday life. In experiential learning, the educator acts as a facilitator in the child's process of discovery, providing necessary resources, sharing insights, and guiding children when they encounter difficulties.

In outdoor education, children can acquire knowledge within contexts that promote understanding and practical application of new concepts—factors that enhance the learning process (comprehension, retention, application). Through activities that promote learning in natural settings, recreational and enjoyable experiences, personal and social development programmes, nature walks, and mountain excursions, these approaches rely on practical learning experiences that aim to build children's abilities while drawing on the rich resources of the natural environment.

Siraj-Blatchford (2001) describes an educational practice in which children are encouraged to explore, investigate, and gain experience with scientific content through play, with the educator's role being to lay the foundations for an exploratory approach (Siraj-Blatchford, in Henriksson, Leden, & Fridberg, 2025). PLAY-BASED learning revives certain directions from the Montessori educational model, particularly the emphasis on active child

engagement through individualized learning tasks, fine-motor activities, and the promotion of self-esteem. Influences of socio-constructivism are evident in the trust that education must place in children as they construct knowledge and develop autonomy, focusing on social interactions, social problem solving, and peer learning. In this context, the educational environment seeks to honour children's needs: the need to be respected, the need for social inclusion, the need for active engagement, and the need to feel responsible, among others.

The role of integration in early childhood education is to facilitate the harmonious development of all children by promoting social, emotional, and communication skills. Integration supports children in learning to interact, collaborate, develop empathy, and build healthy self-esteem, thereby preparing them for more successful participation in society.

2.3. CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) in Early Childhood Education

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) has emerged as a significant pedagogical approach within early childhood education, responding to the increasing need for multilingual competencies in contemporary societies. CLIL promotes the simultaneous development of subject-related knowledge and an additional language, providing young children with meaningful opportunities to engage in linguistic and cognitive growth through integrated learning experiences.

In early childhood settings, CLIL is not conceived as a formal or disciplinarily rigid method; instead, it is adapted to the developmental characteristics of young learners, who acquire knowledge primarily through exploration, interaction, and play (Mehisto, 2021). At this age, language development is closely intertwined with sensory-motor experiences, social engagement, and emotional security. Consequently, CLIL activities are designed

to embed the foreign language within authentic, age-appropriate contexts—storytelling, hands-on exploration, thematic learning centres, music, movement, and play-based tasks.

Research demonstrates that early exposure to a second language within meaningful contexts supports not only linguistic development but also cognitive flexibility, executive functioning, and socio-emotional competencies (Nikolov & Mihaljević Djigunović, 2019). Through CLIL, children become accustomed to switching between languages, interpreting multimodal messages, and engaging with content in more complex ways. Such experiences contribute to the development of metalinguistic awareness and foster a positive disposition toward linguistic and cultural diversity.

The educator plays a decisive role in ensuring the success of CLIL in early education. Beyond being a language model, the educator functions as a designer of learning environments that encourage curiosity, communication, and collaborative meaning-making. Strategies frequently used in early CLIL include scaffolding, visual support, demonstration, repetition through varied contexts, routines that reinforce vocabulary, and the use of gestures and real objects to anchor understanding (Coyle, Hood, & Marsh, 2010). These strategies ensure that children engage actively with both the content and the language, without experiencing cognitive overload.

Furthermore, CLIL aligns naturally with integrated and interdisciplinary curricular approaches that define modern early childhood education. Because themes in early childhood programmes typically cut across multiple developmental and learning areas—nature, community, health, creativity - CLIL can be embedded fluidly within broader learning experiences. For example, thematic projects involving science exploration, environmental awareness, or

cultural traditions offer rich contexts for introducing and consolidating foreign-language vocabulary and communicative structures.

Implementing CLIL in early education also contributes to building inclusive learning environments. By valuing linguistic plurality and offering multiple modes of expression, CLIL creates opportunities for children with diverse linguistic backgrounds to participate equitably in classroom life. The approach supports social interaction, peer learning, and the development of empathy and intercultural understanding, fundamental competencies in a globalised world.

In sum, CLIL represents a forward-looking pedagogical approach that strengthens both language learning and holistic development in early childhood. When implemented thoughtfully—through play, exploration, and multimodal communication—it becomes a powerful tool for enriching children’s learning experiences and preparing them for future educational pathways.

CLIL in early childhood education supports holistic development by intertwining language learning with exploration, creativity, and social interaction. Its strengths lie in promoting multilingual competencies from an early age, enhancing cognitive flexibility, enriching thematic, interdisciplinary learning, and fostering intercultural attitudes and socio-emotional skills. For sustainable implementation, educational systems must provide coherent policy frameworks, robust teacher training, developmentally appropriate resources, and institutional support for innovative, integrated pedagogies. As early childhood education continues to evolve toward inclusive, child-centred models, CLIL offers a powerful avenue for enriching learning experiences and preparing children to navigate an increasingly interconnected world.

3. Conclusion

Early childhood education is not merely a preparatory stage for school; it represents the foundation upon which a child's entire development is built. Children's experiences in early childhood programmes can have a profound influence on their cognitive, social, and emotional development (Donoghue, 2017; Hanno, Jones, & Lexaus, 2021). Through interaction with peers and educators, children develop cognitive, social, and emotional skills that prepare them for future challenges. The importance of early childhood education is underscored by numerous studies showing that children who benefit from well-structured educational programmes in their early years develop stronger competencies in areas such as communication, creativity, and critical thinking.

To enhance the quality of early childhood education and care, educational policies increasingly focus on creating multidisciplinary standards, establishing state-level systems for quality evaluation and improvement, strengthening national regulations, and initiating innovative interdisciplinary partnerships.

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